

Carboxylic group stretching frequency of the free ligands (Npa, PIC and FA) at 1700 cm^{-1} was lowered to 1650 cm^{-1} in the complexes showing coordination of metal through carboxylate group³. The free ligand (Npa) shows a band around $3030-3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH) which is shifted to the lower frequency region in the case of complex, suggesting the coordination of NH group. The strong to medium intensity bands at $1010-1040\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to C-O-C stretch of furan ring in the free ligand. Considerable shift in case of M(Npa)(FA).H₂O complexes suggests furan ring oxygen coordination⁴. The free ligands (Npa and PIC) ring breathing modes⁵ at $\sim 1170\text{ cm}^{-1}$ shifted to lower frequency in case of the metal complexes, which indicates the coordination of pyridine nitrogen. Some new ir bands at $480-500$ and $410-430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the metal complexes are due to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} vibrations^{6,7} respectively.

The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes exhibit a broad band at 14040 and 14188 cm^{-1} in case of Cu(Npa)(PIC).H₂O and Cu(Npa)(FA).H₂O respectively, due to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in a distorted octahedral geometry⁸. This is well supported by the μ_{eff} values. The electronic spectra of Ni(Npa)(PIC).H₂O and Ni(Npa)(FA).H₂O complexes exhibit two bands, ν_1 at $9610, 9995\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and ν_2 at $16390, 16393\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The third band (ν_3) appears as a shoulder at 24690 cm^{-1} . Spectral data together with μ_{eff} value ($3.2-3.3$ B.M.) reveal an octahedral geometry for Ni^{II}⁹. The values of Racah parameter B ($816, 740\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are less than the free-ion value (1070 cm^{-1}) suggesting a considerable orbital overlap and delocalisation of electron in the metal ligand bond. ν_2/ν_1 value of 1.70 and 1.69 are close to those ($1.64-1.8$)¹⁰ expected for octahedral geometry. The electronic spectra of Co(Npa)(PIC).H₂O and Co(Npa)(FA).H₂O correspond to typical octahedral symmetry. Three bands at ($7610, 7560$), ($16339, 16337$) and ($20040, 19500$) cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_3) transitions respectively. The ligand field parameters Dq , B , β and LFSE and μ_{eff} values ($4.8-5.1$ B.M.) and ν_2/ν_1 value of 1.4 and 2.16 respectively suggest distorted octahedral environment around Co^{II}.

Fungicidal screening: The study reveals (Table 2) that the ligands are fungitoxic and their activity increases with the increase in concentration. The metal complexes are more active than the corresponding free ligands. The growth inhibition capacity of the complexes follow the order, $\text{Co}^{II} > \text{Ni}^{II} > \text{Cu}^{II}$.

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Complexes of Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) with 2-Hydroxy-5 methylacetophenone Thiosemicarbazone

K. K. ARAVINDAKSHAN

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Kerala-673 635

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2-HYDROXY-5-methylacetophenone thiosemicarbazone has been used as an analytical reagent for metal ions¹. Although the preparation of some of its metal complexes and their base adducts have been mentioned^{2,3} in literature, detailed studies have not been carried out. Moreover, as we have observed some remarkable differences in composition and structure of the complexes in our investigations, we considered it worthwhile to report them along with the new complexes of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone thiosemicarbazone (LH₂) was synthesised⁴ and recrystallised from methanol. For the preparation of the complexes of the type M(L).nH₂O, where, M = Co^{II} or Ni^{II}, n = 0.5; and M = Zn^{II}, n = 0, a hot aqueous solution of the respective metal acetate (10 mmol) was added dropwise to a refluxing methanolic solution of the ligand (10 mmol) containing sodium acetate (1.0 g). The resulting solid complexes were washed with water and methanol, and dried under reduced pressure over P₂O₅. The mixed halo complexes of the metals were prepared by adding a methanolic solution of the corresponding metal halide (10 mmol) to a refluxing methanolic solution (20 mmol) of the ligand. In the cases of Fe^{III}-chloride, Cd^{II}-chloride and -bromide and

Hg^{II}-halide complexes, 10 mmol solution of the ligand was used. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The chloride and bromide complexes of Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} separated as yellow solids. The Ni^{II} halide complexes were separated by concentrating the resulting solution to 20% of its original volume. In all other cases the resulting solution was concentrated to get a pasty mass which on subsequent cooling separated the solid complexes. The complexes were filtered, washed with small quantities of methanol and dried under reduced pressure over P₄O₁₀.

The complexes were characterised by elemental analysis, conductance (~ 10⁻³M solution in methanol and in nitrobenzene), magnetic moment (at 28 ± 2°), reflectance and ir (KBr) spectral data. Thermograms were recorded at a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ and with 2–6 mg sample.

Results and Discussion

The two nickel halide complexes Ni(LH₂)₂X₂·2H₂O (X=Cl, Br) behave as 1:2 electrolytes in methanol⁴. All the other complexes behave as non-electrolytes both in methanol and nitrobenzene. The lower magnetic moment (5.25 B.M.) of [Fe(LH₂)Cl₂] may be due to a high-spin-low-spin equilibrium⁵. Magnetic moment of 2.30 B.M. of the Co^{II} complex suggests a square-planar configuration⁶. The diamagnetic behaviour of Ni(L)O·5H₂O reveals its square-planar geometry⁶. Magnetic moment values of 3.01 and 3.09 B.M. respectively for [Ni(LH₂)₂]X₂·2H₂O (where X=Cl or Br) correspond to octahedral Ni^{II} ion⁶. The 440 and 535 nm weak bands in the reflectance spectra of [Fe(LH₂)Cl₂] may be assigned to spin-forbidden transitions ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g} and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g} respectively⁷. The shoulder at 1 030 nm and broad

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Analysis % : Found (Calcd)			Halogen	Λ_M Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	
	Metal	N	S		Methanol	Nitrobenzene
Co(L)O·5H ₂ O	21.00 (20.38)	14.80 (14.53)	11.42 (11.08)	–	2.5	0.6
Ni(L)O·5H ₂ O	20.89 (20.31)	14.98 (14.54)	11.35 (11.09)	–	1.8	0.5
Zn(L)	22.73 (22.80)	14.88 (14.66)	11.08 (11.18)	–	1.3	0.2
[Fe(LH ₂)Cl ₂]	14.50 (14.49)	10.52 (10.90)	8.50 (8.32)	26.95 (27.59)	129.9	0.9
[Ni(LH ₂) ₂]Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	9.38 (9.59)	13.56 (13.73)	10.48 (10.47)	11.50 (11.58)	196.3	–
[Ni(LH ₂) ₂]Br ₂ ·2H ₂ O	8.40 (8.37)	12.07 (11.99)	9.30 (9.14)	22.18 (22.79)	202.5	–
[Zn(LH ₂) ₂]Cl ₂]	11.10 (11.21)	14.32 (14.42)	10.81 (11.00)	12.04 (12.16)	38.5	0.5
[Zn(LH ₂) ₂]Br ₂]	9.55 (9.73)	12.38 (12.51)	9.70 (9.54)	23.54 (23.79)	64.5	1.2
[Zn(LH ₂) ₂]I ₂ ·2H ₂ O	8.09 (8.15)	10.38 (10.48)	7.89 (8.00)	31.08 (31.65)	93.0	1.9
[Cd(LH ₂)Cl ₂]·H ₂ O	26.42 (26.47)	9.20 (9.90)	7.34 (7.55)	16.58 (16.70)	80.2	0.1
[Cd(LH ₂)Br ₂]·H ₂ O	21.87 (21.90)	8.05 (8.18)	6.11 (6.24)	31.55 (31.12)	55.3	0.2
[Cd(LH ₂) ₂]I ₂ ·2H ₂ O	13.20 (13.24)	10.13 (9.90)	7.33 (7.55)	29.95 (29.90)	28.1	2.0
[Hg(LH ₂)Cl ₂]·H ₂ O	39.06 (39.12)	8.16 (8.20)	6.12 (6.25)	13.73 (13.83)	64.7	1.4
[Hg(LH ₂)Br ₂]·H ₂ O	33.30 (33.34)	6.79 (6.98)	5.31 (5.33)	26.35 (26.56)	28.5	1.4
[Hg(LH ₂)I ₂]·H ₂ O	28.74 (28.63)	6.33 (6.04)	4.70 (4.61)	36.40 (36.48)	11.3	2.9

band of weak intensity at 1 100 nm in the reflectance spectra of $\text{Co(L)O.5H}_2\text{O}$ are due to $d \rightarrow d$ transitions, characteristic of square-planar geometry⁶. $\text{Ni(L)O.5H}_2\text{O}$ has a broad medium intensity band at 710 nm which is assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transition, typical of square-planar Ni^{2+} complex⁶. The absorption bands of strong intensities around 490, 720 and 1 100 nm in the reflectance spectra of Ni^{2+} halide complexes are assigned to transitions, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ respectively. These bands are characteristic of octahedral stereochemistry around the Ni^{2+} ion⁶.

The broad bands of medium intensities or distinct shoulders due to ν_{OH} around $3\,550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ir spectra of all the complexes except those of Zn(L) , $[\text{Fe(LH}_2\text{)Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Zn(LH}_2\text{)}_2\text{X}_2]$ (where $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br) indicate the presence of water molecules in them⁹. The strong intensity bands around $3\,300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the ligand and the complexes may be assigned to ν_{NH} stretching modes of NH_2 and NH groups⁹. The broad band of very strong intensity at $3\,160\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand spectrum can be assigned to stretching mode of hydrogen bonded OH group⁹. In the spectra of the Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} complexes of general formula $\text{M(L).nH}_2\text{O}$, this band is not present which indicates the displacement of hydroxy proton by the respective metal ion during complexation. The absence of any band in the region $2\,650\text{--}2\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand spectrum indicates that there is no SH group in the free ligand in the solid state⁹. The ligand band at $1\,575\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to azomethine stretch⁹ shifted to lower wave number by about $10\text{--}15\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes. This indicates the coordination of the ligand through this nitrogen in all the complexes. A medium intensity band at 850 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum may be attributed to pure $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$. In the spectra of $\text{M(L).nH}_2\text{O}$ complexes this band disappears and a new band appears around 680 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{S}$ region)⁹. The large shift of this band to lower frequency in these complexes is the strongest evidence for coordination through the sulphur atom of $\text{HN}=\text{C}=\text{S}$ group of the ligand after enolisation to $\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{SH}$ and deprotonation⁹. In all other complexes the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretching band shifted to lower frequency region (around 770 cm^{-1}) indicating coordination through thiocarbonyl sulphur ($\text{C}=\text{S}$) without enolisation¹⁰. The medium intensity bands at $625\text{--}600$ and $505\text{--}495\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}=\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}=\text{N}}$ respectively.

The thermogravimetric studies of the complexes clearly indicate that the associated water molecules were the lattice-held ones as they were lost around 120° . The complexes containing no water molecules i.e. Zn(L) , $[\text{Fe(LH}_2\text{)Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Zn(LH}_2\text{)}_2\text{X}_2]$ (where, $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br) are stable at 200° .

Thus on the basis of the foregoing discussion it is inferred that the ligand coordinates with the central metal ion in three different ways, such as

(i) bivalent (L^{2-}) tridentate, as in the complexes of general formula $\text{M(L).nH}_2\text{O}$, (ii) neutral tridentate, as in $[\text{Fe(LH}_2\text{)Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Ni(LH}_2\text{)}_2\text{X}_2.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and (iii) neutral bidentate, as in the halogeno complexes of Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Hg^{2+} .

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Thermodynamics of Transport of Water Across Different Cation-saturated Kaolinite Clay

S. K. SANYAL* and A. BHATTACHARJYA

Department of Agricultural Chemistry & Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235

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REPORTS on studies of thermal diffusion of water in soil¹⁻⁴ are available although the qualitative aspects of the latter received scant attention. More recently, Sanyal *et al.*⁵⁻⁷ re-examined the thermodynamic theories of thermal diffusion and pointed out the significance of heat and entropy of transport in characterising the soil-moisture interactions. The present paper extends these ideas to diffusional transport of water across clays and examines the findings in the light of clay-water interactions.

Experimental

The clays used were kaolinite in K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} -saturated form. They were prepared by converting the crude kaolinite clay to H^+ -form by treating it with 0.05 M HCl , followed by removal of the excess chloride on dialysis through cellophane